

Detecting Chirality-Induced Spin Selectivity in Randomly Oriented Radical Pairs Photogenerated by Hole Transfer

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ABSTRACT

Chirality induced spin selectivity (CISS) has the potential to control the spin dynamics of chiral molecules for applications in quantum information science. Here we investigate the effect of CISS on the spin dynamics of radical pair formation following photo-driven hole transfer in a pair of donor-chiral bridge-acceptor (D-B χ -A) enantiomers, where D = 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl[1,3]-dioxolo[4,5-f][1,3]benzodioxole, B χ = (*R*)- or (*S*)-2,2'-dimethoxy-4,4'-diphenyl-5,5',6,6',7,7',8,8'-octahydro-1,1'-binaphthalene, and A = naphthalene-(1,4:5,8)-bis(dicarboximide). The results are compared to those obtained on the corresponding achiral D-B-A molecule in which B = 2'',3',5',6''-tetramethyl-1,1':4',1'':4'',1'''-quaterphenyl. Photoexcitation of A in a randomly oriented sample of D-B χ -A in glassy butyronitrile at 85 K results in subnanosecond two-step hole transfer from ^{1*}A to D to form D⁺-B χ -A⁻, which was characterized using time-resolved electron paramagnetic resonance (TREPR) spectroscopy at X (9.6 GHz), Q (34 GHz), and W (94 GHz) bands. The spectra show lineshape changes that are characteristic of a ~38% contribution of CISS to the spin dynamics of D⁺-B χ -A⁻ formation. The lineshape changes resulting from CISS are particularly apparent in the TREPR spectra at X-band as predicted by recent theory. These results show that 1) CISS has a significant influence on radical pair dynamics initiated by photo-driven hole transfer, which is complementary to our recent electron transfer results, and 2) CISS can be detected using TREPR on radical pairs that are randomly oriented relative to an external magnetic field.

INTRODUCTION

Quantum information science (QIS) stands to benefit from chemical synthesis, as it offers the ability to build QIS systems using a bottom up approach.¹ The quantum properties of molecular qubits can be synthetically tuned to afford precise control over quantum states.¹ One such property is chirality, which has been shown to control the spin states of electrons through the chirality induced spin selectivity (CISS) effect.²⁻³ This effect has been demonstrated even at room temperature, affording the potential for quantum devices based on chirality to operate at such practical temperatures.² Theoretical work has already explored approaches to implementing chirality in quantum processing, such as in spin-correlated radical pairs (SCRPs)⁴⁻⁹ and electron transfer dyads attached to stable radical qubits.^{7,9}

While a comprehensive theoretical understanding of the CISS effect remains to be established, two main types of theories attempt to explain spin polarization arising from the CISS effect.³ The first type focuses on spin-orbit coupling (SOC) within the chiral molecule; however, since large spin polarizations are observed in organic molecules composed only of low atomic number elements possessing weak SOC, this model predicts effects that are orders of magnitude lower than those observed. To amplify the effects of SOC, modifications to this model include adding contributions from electron-electron exchange,¹⁰ nuclear vibrations,¹¹⁻¹² and electron-phonon scattering.³ The second main class is the spinterface model, in which interactions between the chiral molecule and the metal surface to which it is attached provide the large SOC needed to observe the CISS effect.^{3,13} Therefore, building a satisfactory model of the CISS effect requires decoupling the potential effect of the metal surface from the intrinsic chirality of the molecules.

This separation can be accomplished using methods to probe the spin dynamics within the molecule itself.^{4-9, 14-16} To that end, theory suggests that CISS should affect the spin dynamics of

spin-correlated radical pairs (SCRPs)¹⁷⁻¹⁹ produced by photo-driven charge transfer in donor-chiral bridge-acceptor (D-B χ -A) molecules.⁴⁻⁹ For example, using time-resolved electron paramagnetic resonance (TREPR) spectroscopy, Privitera, et al.¹⁴ observed SCRPs composed of CdSe quantum dots (QD), a chiral peptide bridge, and a C₆₀ electron acceptor, but it proved difficult to assign the spectral changes to CISS because the QDs intrinsically produce a mixed singlet-triplet initial state. This led to a focus on fully organic D-B χ -A triads that produce singlet-born radical pairs following photoexcitation and are better able, in principle, to display the signatures of CISS in TREPR spectra than SCRPs produced initially with mixed singlet-triplet character.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ Our previous work demonstrated how CISS affects the TREPR spectra of singlet-born SCRPs resulting from two-step sub-nanosecond electron transfer within a D-B χ -A triad following selective photoexcitation of the donor.¹⁶ The CISS effect became apparent only when the long axis of the D-B χ -A molecule was aligned perpendicular to the external magnetic field. Moreover, simulations of the D^{•+}-B χ -A^{•-} spin dynamics suggest that, given favorable radical pair magnetic parameters, CISS signatures can appear in randomly oriented (powder) TREPR spectra of SCRPs, further simplifying the experimental assessment of the CISS effect.⁷⁻⁸

To evaluate this possibility, we performed TREPR experiments at X (9.6 GHz), Q (34 GHz), and W (94 GHz) bands on a new series of chiral D-B χ -A and achiral D-B-A systems, where D = 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-f][1,3]benzodioxole (BDX), B χ = (*R*)- or (*S*)-2,2'-dimethoxy-4,4'-diphenyl-5,5',6,6',7,7',8,8'-octahydro-1,1'-binaphthalene, B = 2'',3'',5'',6''-tetramethyl-1,1':4',1'':4'',1'''-quarterphenyl, and A = naphthalene-(1,4:5,8)-bis(dicarboximide) (NDI). Upon selective photoexcitation of A, D-B χ -A undergoes two-step hole transfer D-B χ -^{1*}A → D-B χ ^{•+}-A^{•-} → D^{•+}-B χ -A^{•-} to form an SCRPs that shows clear signatures of CISS in the lineshape of the TREPR spectra, when compared to those of achiral D^{•+}-B-A^{•-}, demonstrating the ability of the chiral bridge to

Figure 1. A) Structures of chiral triads (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** and the achiral triad reference (**2**). B) Jablonski diagram of hole transfer and charge recombination.

influence spin dynamics during a hole transfer process and complementing our previous results on electron transfer.¹⁶ Furthermore, judicious selection of radical ions possessing advantageous magnetic properties, such as 1) the orientation of the *g*-tensor of BDX with respect to that of NDI and 2) the relatively low *g*-tensor anisotropy of BDX, afforded the ability to observe signatures of CISS in the TREPR spectra of D⁺⁺-B_χ-A⁻ even in a randomly oriented sample in a frozen glassy solvent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis. Synthetic details are provided in the Supporting Information. To access (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1** and **2** quickly and in plentiful supply, a convergent synthesis approach was employed. The optically active chiral bridge in (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** is a BINOL derived 1,1'-5,5',6,6',7,7',8,8'-octahydro-1,1'-binaphthalene unit, which has been used previously in the construction of metal-organic coordination cages.¹⁹ We modified this existing work slightly, electing to protect the bridge oxygen atoms with a methyl group as opposed to an ethyl group. The final step of the convergent

synthesis utilizes a one-pot Suzuki-Miyaura coupling reaction, where (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** were prepared by reacting (*S*)- and (*R*)- 4,4'-dibromo-2,2'-dimethoxy-3,3'-dimethyl-5,5',6,6',7,7',8,8'-octahydro-1,1'-binaphthalene with *N*-cyclohexyl-*N'*-(4'-(4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)phenyl)-NDI and 3'-(4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)phenyl)-BDX building blocks. The achiral D-B-A reference molecule (**2**) was prepared via the same approach, with the 4,4'-diiodo-2,2,6,6-tetramethylbiphenyl achiral bridge²⁰ being at the center of the convergent synthesis.

Charge Transfer Energetics. The free energies of each electron transfer reaction for D-B χ -A and D-B-A in a frozen butyronitrile (PrCN) glass were estimated using the lowest singlet excited state energy of A ($E_s = 3.20$ eV),²¹ and the measured one-electron redox potentials of D ($E_{ox} = 0.80$ V), A ($E_{red} = -0.62$ V), B χ ($E_{ox} = 1.5$ V) and B ($E_{ox} = 1.76$ V) with all potentials referenced relative to a saturated calomel electrode (Figures S5 and S6). The center-to-center ionic distances in D-B χ^+ -A $^-$ and D $^{*+}$ -B χ -A $^-$ are 12.4 Å and 23.7 Å, respectively, and were determined experimentally using pulse-EPR techniques (see the Supporting Information, Figure S13, and Table S1) as well as computed using density functional theory (DFT) (Table S1). Using these data and the estimated dielectric constant of PrCN at 105 K ($\epsilon_s = 2.3$)²² in the Weller equation,²³ the energies for D-B χ^+ -A $^-$ and D $^{*+}$ -B χ -A $^-$ are 2.5 eV and 2.0 eV, respectively, above the ground state (Figure 1b).

Absorption and Circular Dichroism (CD) Spectroscopy. The UV-vis spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** are identical, while that of **2** has a somewhat stronger absorbance at wavelengths <350 nm (Figure 2a). The spectra are dominated by the NDI absorption bands at 378, 358, and 342 nm. The spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** are approximately an additive combination of those of BDX, (*S*)- or (*R*)-B χ and NDI, thus indicating that the electronic coupling between these redox components is relatively weak. Circular dichroism (CD) spectra of each enantiomer show the expected mirror

image

Figure 2. (a) UV-vis absorption spectra of (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1**, and **2** recorded in 1,4-dioxane at 295 K. (b) CD spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** recorded in 1,4-dioxane at 295 K.

symmetry over the absorption range of the $B\chi$ chiral bridge molecule (Figure 2b), which is in full agreement with the CD spectra reported previously for (*R*)- or (*S*)-2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5',6,6',7,7',8,8'-octahydro-1,1'-binaphthalene.²⁴

Transient Absorption Spectroscopy. The charge transfer dynamics of (*S*)-**1** in PrCN at 105 K were measured using a 120-fs pump pulse and probing between 100 fs-250 μ s (Figures 3a, 3b, S7, and S8). The femtosecond data were probed between 370-1600 nm to monitor the hole transfer dynamics; charge recombination in the nano-to-microsecond regime was monitored between 380-900 nm. Evolution-associated spectra from global fitting of each time domain is shown in Figures S7 and S8. Following photoexcitation of NDI at 355 nm, the $^1N^*$ NDI excited-state absorption (ESA) at 585 and 1100 nm is observed briefly prior to being replaced by the features of $NDI^{\cdot-}$ at 477, 605, 670, and 745 nm²⁵ within the first picosecond ($\tau_{CS1} < 0.3$ ps). These bands are accompanied by a broad, featureless absorption at 1100-1600 nm in the near-infrared (NIR) region that does not belong to $NDI^{\cdot-}$ and is assigned to the *p*-quaterphenyl π -system of $B\chi^{\cdot+}$.²⁶ These features all

decrease in amplitude over the next nanosecond, with some spectral evolution in the NIR region,

Figure 3. a) Femtosecond and b) nanosecond transient absorption data following 355 nm excitation of (*S*)-**1** in PrCN at 105 K at the indicated pump-probe delay times. c) Femtosecond and d) nanosecond transient absorption data following 355 nm excitation of **2** in PrCN at 105 K at the indicated pump-probe delay times.

then decay completely, leaving only the $\text{NDI}^{\bullet-}$ bands as the hole arrives at BDX with $\tau_{\text{CS}2} = 211 \pm 1$ ps. Nanosecond transient absorption spectroscopy shows that the radical pair relaxes and recombines with several time constants due to distributed kinetics within the low-temperature matrix, the longest of which is $\tau_{\text{CR}} = 248 \pm 3$ μs . Spectral evolution and charge transfer time constants for the (*R*)-**1** enantiomer (Figures S9 and S10) are very similar.

The TA spectra of the achiral reference molecule **2** at 105 K in PrCN using 355 nm excitation are shown in Figures 3c, 3d, S11, and S12. The data and kinetics are similar to those of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1**, with rapid hole transfer to B in $\tau_{CS1} < 0.3$ ps to form B^{*+} , although the NIR ESA bands associated with B^{*+} occur at 965 nm and are blue-shifted relative to those of $B\chi^{*+}$. This shift most likely results from the nearly perpendicular conformation of the 2,2,6,6-tetramethylbiphenyl segment of B^{*+} , which reduces π -conjugation through the *p*-quarterphenyl length of B^{*+} .²⁷ This feature appears immediately upon hole transfer, then decays completely to the baseline with hole trapping by BDX with $\tau_{CS2} = 815 \pm 40$ ps. Recombination occurs with multiple rates, similar to the chiral compounds with the longest time constant $\tau_{CR} = 270 \pm 40$ μ s.

TREPR spectra of SCRPs in the presence of CISS. The spin Hamiltonian describing a SCRPs is composed of the electron Zeeman interaction for donor and acceptor spins, their corresponding electron-nuclear hyperfine interactions, and the spin-spin isotropic exchange and anisotropic dipolar couplings.²⁸

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\mu_B}{h} \mathbf{B}_0 \mathbf{g}_D \hat{S}_D + \frac{\mu_B}{h} \mathbf{B}_0 \mathbf{g}_A \hat{S}_A + J \hat{S}_D \hat{S}_A + \hat{S}_D \mathbf{D}_{DA} \hat{S}_A + \hat{H}_{HF} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{B}_0 is the external magnetic field, \mathbf{g}_D and \mathbf{g}_A are the *g* tensors of the donor and acceptor spins, *J* is the isotropic exchange interaction, and the dipolar coupling \mathbf{D}_{DA} is a matrix with diagonal elements [*d* *d* $-2d$], where:

$$d = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi h} \frac{g_D g_A \mu_B^2}{r^3} (1 - 3 \cos^2 \theta) \quad (2)$$

and *r* is the distance between is the distance between the centers of the donor and acceptor spin, which was determined experimentally by out-of-phase electron spin echo envelope modulation (OOP-ESEEM) measurements (see the Supporting Information and Figure S13) and corroborated by DFT calculations (Figure S14). Due to the large radical pair distance (*vide infra*), $J \cong 0$.

Diagonalization of the SCRPs Hamiltonian yields the eigenstates:

$$\begin{aligned}
|1\rangle &= |T_{+1}\rangle \\
|2\rangle &= \cos \varphi |S\rangle + \sin \varphi |T_0\rangle \\
|3\rangle &= -\sin \varphi |S\rangle + \cos \varphi |T_0\rangle \\
|4\rangle &= |T_{-1}\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where

$$\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{\mu_B}{\hbar} B_0 (g_D - g_A) + \sum_i (a_{Di} - a_{Ai}) m_i}{J - \frac{d}{2}} \tag{4}$$

For a singlet born radical pair, the two eigenstates with singlet character are populated resulting in four transitions, two emissive and two absorptive, of equal intensity. The initial SCRPs spin state of $D^+ \cdot$ - $B \cdot$ - $A^{\cdot -}$ in achiral **2** was assumed to be a pure singlet and its TREPR spectrum was simulated as such using the Easyspin (dev6.0)²⁹ function *pepper*.

The TREPR spectra of $D^+ \cdot$ - $B \chi$ - $A^{\cdot -}$ in (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** were simulated by incorporating the CISS effect into the model phenomenologically by using the initial spin state defined in eq 5^{4,6} instead of the initial singlet state $|S\rangle$.

$$|\psi_0\rangle = \cos \frac{\chi}{2} |S\rangle + i \sin \frac{\chi}{2} |T_0(n)\rangle \tag{5}$$

In eq 4, the level of chirality is defined by χ , and can range from $\chi = 0$ for 0% CISS to $\chi = \pm\pi/2$ for 100% CISS in each enantiomer (+ or -). The states $|S\rangle$ and $|T_0(n)\rangle$ are the radical pair singlet and triplet states, respectively. The triplet state in eq 5 is defined with respect to the molecular frame and the charge transfer axis through the molecule. This can be reasonably assumed to be collinear with the axis of the dipolar coupling and rotated into the laboratory frame using $e^{-i\theta\hat{S}_y}$ yielding:⁶

$$e^{-i\theta\hat{S}_y} |\psi_0\rangle = |\psi_0(\theta)\rangle = \cos \frac{\chi}{2} |S\rangle + i \sin \frac{\chi}{2} \left[\cos \theta |T_0\rangle + \frac{\sin \theta}{\sqrt{2}} (|T_{-1}\rangle - |T_{+1}\rangle) \right] \tag{6}$$

where θ is the angle between the molecular axis and the magnetic field. From eq 6 it is clear to see that when CISS is present, the triplet levels $|T_{-1}\rangle$ and $|T_{+1}\rangle$ are populated when $\theta > 0$, which results

in a change in the amplitude of the absorption and emission features of the spectrum, especially when the charge transfer axis of the molecule is aligned perpendicular to the external magnetic field.^{7-8, 16} However, even in an isotropic ensemble of radical pairs, the dipolar coupling of the two spins comprising the radical pair does not integrate to zero.⁷⁻⁸ The inclusion of the CISS contribution changes the relative ratios of the radical pair transition intensities, which, in turn, results in lineshape changes that depend on the orientations of the *g*-tensors of the radicals relative to each other and to the external magnetic field as well as the orientation of the dipolar axis relative to the external magnetic field. In addition, the spectrum of an ensemble of randomly oriented radical pairs does not depend on the sign of χ , so that the spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** should be identical.⁷⁻⁸

TREPR Spectroscopy. TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1**, and **2** in PrCN at 85 K were obtained initially at X-band. Direct detection was used such that positive signals in the resulting spin-polarized spectra denote enhanced absorption (*a*) and negative signals denote emission (*e*). The X-band spectrum for **2** is shown in Figure 4a and exhibits an *ea**e* polarization pattern. The simulation of the TREPR spectrum of **2** assumes that the radical pair is born in the singlet state and uses the *g*-tensors and other magnetic parameters of BDX⁺⁺ and NDI⁻ given in Table S2. Significant changes are observed in the TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** (Figure 4b) relative to that of **2**. While all spectra exhibit the *ea**e* polarization pattern, the spectra of both (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** show an increase in the intensity of the low-field emission feature and a decrease in the intensity of the high-field emission feature when compared to the spectrum of achiral **2**. The simulations indicate that this change results from a $38 \pm 4\%$ contribution of CISS.

TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1**, and **2** at Q- and W-bands are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. The increased spectra resolution results in the spectra of **2** (Figures 5a and 6a) having

Figure 4. Experimental TREPR spectra at X-band (9.6 GHz) in PrCN at 85 K, 100 ns after a 355-nm, 7-ns laser pulse. (a) **2** (black trace), (b) (*S*)-**1** (black trace) and (*R*)-**1** (blue trace). Simulations of the spectra (red traces) used the parameters given in Table S2. The field was frequency-corrected.

an *eaee* polarization pattern. Changes in the relative intensities of each transition are shown in the spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** (Figures 5b and 6b), particularly an increase in the lowest-field emission feature and a decrease in the highest-field emission features. Simulations of the TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1**, and **2** at W-band, where spectral separation of the $\text{BDX}^{+\cdot}$ and $\text{NDI}^{\cdot-}$ resonances are maximal, indicate that these transitions result from the $g_{x,y}$ components of the $\text{NDI}^{\cdot-}$ and $\text{BDX}^{+\cdot}$ g -tensors and the g_z component of the $\text{NDI}^{\cdot-}$ g -tensor, respectively. The contribution of CISS needed to simulate these spectra is a bit lower than that for the X-band spectra. The CISS contribution at Q-band is $21 \pm 5\%$ and at W-band is $29 \pm 8\%$. The TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** are the same at X-, Q- and W-bands, indicating that the handedness of chirality does not affect the measurement, consistent with theory⁷⁻⁸ and our previous results.¹⁶

Importantly, spectral changes resulting from the CISS effect are observed in the powder spectra, despite a lack of any molecular alignment. As noted above, in an isotropic ensemble of radical pairs, spherical integration does not cancel out the CISS effect on the spectra, resulting in discernable differences in the lineshape of the $\text{D}^{+\cdot}\text{-B}\chi\text{-A}^{\cdot-}$ TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1**

Figure 5. Experimental TREPR spectra at Q-band (34 GHz) in PrCN at 85 K, 100 ns after a 355-nm, 7-ns laser pulse. (a) **2** (black trace), (b) (*S*)-**1** (black trace) and (*R*)-**1** (blue trace). Simulations of the spectra (red traces) used the parameters given in Table S2. The field was frequency-corrected.

Figure 6. Experimental TREPR spectra at W-band (94 GHz) in PrCN at 85 K, 100 ns after a 355-nm, 7-ns laser pulse. (a) **2** (black trace), (b) (*S*)-**1** (black trace) and (*R*)-**1** (blue trace). Simulations of the spectra (red traces) used the parameters given in Table S2. The field was frequency-corrected.

relative to that of D^+-B-A^- in **2**.⁷⁻⁸ While the spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** change with respect to that of **2** at all three frequencies, the changes are most apparent at X band. This was predicted by Ren and Hore,⁸ who attributed this trend to there being more severe cancellations of emissive and absorptive transitions at lower frequency due to lower resolution and therefore greater overlap of

Figure 7. Simulations of TREPR spectra of $D^{\bullet+}-B\chi-A^{\bullet-}$ with varying contributions of CISS at (a) X-band, (b) Q-band, and (c) W-band. The parameters used in the simulations are given in Table S2.

the different transitions. This is shown in our simulations in which CISS is increased from 0-100% at X-, Q-, and W-bands (Figure 7). As the level of CISS increases, the phase of the spectrum changes to a greater extent. This is most dramatic at X-band, while at Q- and W-bands it is more apparent which transitions are changing in phase, namely those from $\text{BDX}^{*+} g_{x,y}$ and $\text{NDI}^- g_z$. Interestingly, the CISS contribution in the simulated spectra depends on which frequency the measurement is made. The CISS contribution needed to simulate the X- and W-band spectra is about 30-40%, while the corresponding CISS contribution required to simulate the Q-band spectra is about 20-25%. This can be explained in the following manner. In the low frequency regime at X-band all the transitions are overlapping, and the spectrum is only sensitive to parameters such as the CISS contribution χ and the mixing angle ϕ in eq 4, which is high throughout the spectrum. In the high frequency regime, the transitions are more widely separated, and the spectrum is only sensitive to g -anisotropy. Therefore, changing a single parameter, like χ is straightforward. However, the Q-band spectra are in an intermediate regime, where they are sensitive to several parameters, such as χ , ϕ , and g -anisotropy, making them more difficult to simulate. Indeed, the simulations of the $\text{D}^{*+}\text{-B}\chi\text{-A}^-$ TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** at Q-band work well at the low and high field edges of the spectra, where ϕ is low, but breaks down at the center of the spectrum, where ϕ is high.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we observe the influence of CISS on the TREPR spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1**. Photo-driven two-step hole transfer through the chiral bridge in (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** imparts some triplet character to the initial spin state of $\text{D}^{*+}\text{-B}\chi\text{-A}^-$. This can even be seen in the powder spectra of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** when compared to the powder spectrum of **2** and is due to the fact that spherical integration does not cancel the dipolar interaction between the two unpaired spins. This indicates

that not only can CISS be observed in a radical pair photogenerated by hole transfer as opposed to electron transfer, but also can be demonstrated in randomly oriented radical pairs having favorable magnetic parameters in solid solution. The ability to use chirality to control the spin dynamics of spin-correlated radical pairs adds an important control element for manipulating electron spins in potential quantum information applications.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

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NOTES

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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TOC Graphic:

Detecting Chirality Induced Spin Selectivity in Randomly Oriented Radical Pairs Photogenerated by Hole Transfer

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1. Synthesis and Characterization

All commercially available materials were used without further purification unless otherwise noted. All silica gel column chromatography was performed using silica gel from Sorbent Technologies. Characterization of synthesized compounds was performed at the Integrated Molecular Structure Education and Research Center (IMSERC) at Northwestern University. Proton and carbon NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz system equipped with DCH CryoProbe. Chemical shifts are reported in parts-per-million (ppm) relative to TMS. High Resolution Mass Spectra (HRMS) were obtained with an Agilent LCTOF 6200 series mass spectrometer using electrospray ionization (ESI), atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI), and atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI). Circular Dichroism (CD) spectra were obtained using a Jasco J-1700 CD instrument located at the Keck Biophysics Facility at Northwestern University.

Synthesis of the di-bromo bridge **B(χ)-5**.

The synthetic protocols describe the synthesis of the R enantiomers, up to and including **B(R)-(Ph)₂** and **1R**. Reaction yields for the S enantiomers, up to and including **B(S)-(Ph)₂** and **1S**, are noted alongside their characterization data.

Figure S1. Synthesis of the di-bromo bridge **B(χ)-5**.

Reagents and Conditions: **(i)** MeI, K₂CO₃, (CH₃)₂CO, reflux, 24hrs (98%) **(ii)** H₃PO₄: HCl: CH₃COOH (1:1:1), OH(CH₂O)_nH, 90°C, 48hrs **(iii)** LiAlH₄, THF, reflux 6hrs (88% over 2 steps) **(iv)** Br₂, CH₂Cl₂, r.t. 1hr (78%).

Synthesis of B(χ)-2.

B(χ)-2

CAUTION: Methyl Iodide is a known carcinogen. Consult SDS/MSDS.

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with **B(R)-1** (10g, 0.034mol, 1eq), K_2CO_3 (28.17g, 0.204mol, 6eq), and $(CH_3)_2CO$ (200 mL). The reaction mixture was then stirred, followed by careful addition of MeI (21.15 mL, 0.339 mol, 10eq). Stirring was continued, and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux until tlc confirmed that the reaction had reached completion (24hrs). $(CH_3)_2CO$ and excess MeI were removed under reduced pressure. Excess MeI was treated/hydrolyzed with 2M NaOH and discarded accordingly. The reaction mixture was then extracted into CH_2Cl_2 (200 mL) and washed with brine (3 x 100 mL) and water (3 x 100 mL). The CH_2Cl_2 organic layer was then dried (Na_2SO_4), filtered, and removed under reduced pressure. The crude material was then subjected to silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: CH_2Cl_2 / 5:1), yielding **B(R)-2** as a white solid (10.73gs, 98%).

Data for **B(R)-2**.

1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 7.07 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 6.79 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 3.68 (s, 6H), 2.78 (m, 4H), 2.27 (dt, $J = 15$ Hz, 5 Hz, 2H), 2.09 (dt, $J = 15$ Hz, 5 Hz, 2H), 1.77-1.59 (m, 8H).

^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 154.96, 136.99, 129.77, 129.00, 126.13, 109.03, 56.26, 29.68, 27.37, 23.52, 23.43.

ESI-MS calcd. For $C_{22}H_{26}O_2$ ($M+H$) $^+$: 323.2006, found 323.2019.

Data for **B(S)-2**.

Yield 96%.

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.07 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 6.79 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 3.68 (s, 6H), 2.78 (m, 4H), 2.27 (dt, $J = 15$ Hz, 5 Hz, 2H), 2.09 (dt, $J = 15$ Hz, 5 Hz, 2H), 1.77-1.59 (m, 8H).

^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 154.96, 136.99, 129.77, 129.00, 126.13, 109.03, 56.26, 29.68, 27.37, 23.52, 23.43.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ ($\text{M}+\text{H}$) $^+$: 323.2006, found 323.1991.

Synthesis of **B(χ)-3**.

B(χ)-3

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with 85% H_3PO_4 (100 mL), conc. HCl (100 mL), glacial CH_3COOH (100 mL) and **B(R)-2** (10 g, 0.031 mol, 1 eq). The reaction mixture was then stirred, followed by the addition of paraformaldehyde (25 g). The reaction mixture was then heated to 90°C for 48 hrs. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature, followed by extraction with benzene (3 x 100 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (3 x 100 mL), saturated Na_2CO_3 (3 x 100 mL) and water (3 x 100 mL), before being dried over Na_2SO_4 and filtered. The organic layer was then removed under reduced pressure to afford **B(R)-3** as a white solid, which was immediately employed in the next step without further purification.

Data for **B(R)-3**.

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.18 (s, 2H), 4.77 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 4.60 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 3.47 (s, 6H), 2.81 (m, 4H), 2.35-2.22 (m, 4H), 1.79-1.60 (m, 8H).

^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 153.65, 138.23, 133.78, 131.24, 130.85, 128.50, 61.61, 42.05, 29.58, 27.97, 23.09.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_2$ ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$) $^+$: 436.1805, found 436.1808.

Data for **B(S)-3**.

Yield n/a.

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.18 (s, 2H), 4.77 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 4.60 (d, $J = 10$ Hz, 2H), 3.47 (s, 6H), 2.81 (m, 4H), 2.35-2.22 (m, 4H), 1.79-1.60 (m, 8H).

^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 153.65, 138.23, 133.78, 131.24, 130.85, 128.50, 61.61, 42.05, 29.58, 27.97, 23.09.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_2$ ($\text{M}+\text{NH}_4$) $^+$: 436.1805, found 436.1824.

Synthesis of **B(χ)-4**.

B(χ)-4

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with LiAlH_4 (7.06 g, 0.186 mol, 6eq of theoretical max) and anhydrous THF (100 mL). The resulting suspension was stirred, followed by dropwise addition of **B(R)-3** in anhydrous THF (150 mL). Stirring was continued, and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 6 h. Once tlc had confirmed that the reaction had gone to

completion, the reaction was cooled to 0°C using an ice bath. The reaction was carefully quenched by dropwise addition of a THF/water mixture (3:1). The quenched reaction was then poured into a beaker containing 1M H₂SO₄ (100 mL) and a stir bar and was stirred for 30 min. The resulting mixture was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3×100 mL), and the combined organic layers were washed with water (3 x 100 mL) and dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The CH₂Cl₂ was removed under reduced pressure, yielding the crude product which was purified by silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: CH₂Cl₂ / 10:1), yielding **B(R)-4** as a white solid (9.56 g, 88% yield over two steps).

Data for B(R)-4.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 6.94 (s, 2H), 3.43 (s, 6H), 2.76 (m, 4H), 2.29 (s, 6H), 2.30-2.15 (m, 4H), 1.77-1.62 (m, 8H).

¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.88, 134.27, 132.67, 131.12, 131.05, 128.11, 59.85, 29.69, 27.74, 23.45, 16.51.

ESI-MS calcd. For C₂₄H₃₀O₂ (M+H)⁺: 351.2319, found 351.2326.

Data for B(S)-4.

Yield 86% yield over two steps.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 6.94 (s, 2H), 3.43 (s, 6H), 2.76 (m, 4H), 2.29 (s, 6H), 2.30-2.15 (m, 4H), 1.77-1.62 (m, 8H).

¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.88, 134.27, 132.67, 131.12, 131.05, 128.11, 59.85, 29.69, 27.74, 23.45, 16.51.

ESI-MS calcd. For C₂₄H₃₀O₂ (M+H)⁺: 351.2319, found 351.2318.

Synthesis of **B(χ)-5**.

B(χ)-5

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with **B(*R*)-4** (9 g, 0.026 mol, 1eq) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (100 mL). The resulting solution was stirred, followed by dropwise addition of Br_2 (2.63 mL, 0.051 mol, 2eq) in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (20 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at r.t. for 1 hr before being quenched with a saturated NaHSO_3 solution. The quenched reaction mixture was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 x 100 mL), and the combined organic layers were washed with water (3 x 100 mL) and dried over Na_2SO_4 and filtered. The CH_2Cl_2 organic layer was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: CH_2Cl_2 / 15:1), yielding **B(*R*)-5** as a white solid (10.18 g, 78%).

Data for **B(*R*)-5**.

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.40 (s, 6H), 2.79 (m, 4H), 2.40 (s, 6H), 2.31-2.15 (m, 4H), 1.85-1.70 (m, 4H), 1.66-1.54 (m, 4H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 153.91, 135.78, 132.89, 129.95, 129.60, 129.00, 68.43, 31.67, 28.57, 23.71, 22.83, 17.61.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{Br}_2\text{O}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 509.0510, found 509.0509.

Data for B(S)-5.

Yield 79%

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.40 (s, 6H), 2.79 (m, 4H), 2.40 (s, 6H), 2.31-2.15 (m, 4H), 1.85-1.70 (m, 4H), 1.66-1.54 (m, 4H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 153.91, 135.78, 132.89, 129.95, 129.60, 129.00, 68.43, 31.67, 28.57, 23.71, 22.83, 17.61.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{Br}_2\text{O}_2$ $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 509.0510, found 509.0518.

Synthesis of the di-iodo achiral bridge B($\alpha\chi$)-4.

The synthesis of the di-iodo achiral bridge B($\alpha\chi$)-4 has been previously reported.¹

Figure S2. Synthesis of the di-iodo achiral bridge B($\alpha\chi$)-4.

Reagents and Conditions: (i) Zn, aq. NaOH, EtOH, reflux 6hrs (50%) (ii) 10% HCl, reflux 2hrs, pH 10-11 (70%) (iii) NaNO_2 , $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, $\text{I}_2 + \text{KI}$, r.t. overnight (70%).

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.49 (s, 4H), 1.84 (s, 12H).

Synthesis of the NDI-Ph-Bpin building block.

NDI-Ph-Bpin

A two-neck flask equipped with a stir bar was placed under N₂ atmosphere. The flask was then charged with NDA (5g, 18.68 mmol, 1eq), Imidazole (5g, 73.44 mmol, 4eq), and anhydrous DMF (100mL). The 2-neck flask was then equipped with a dropping funnel, with the complete set up placed under N₂ atmosphere. The dropping funnel was charged with DMF (100 mL), n-octylamine (2.93 mL, 17.71 mmol, 0.95eq) and 4-(4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolan-2-yl)aniline (3.88 g, 17.71 mmol, 0.95eq). The 2-neck flask containing NDA, Imidazole and DMF was then heated to 120°C for 1hr (maximizing solubility of NDA), followed by dropwise addition of the dropping funnel solution. Following addition of the amines, the reaction mixture was transferred to an appropriately sized pressure vessel and heated at 180°C for 48hrs.

The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and the DMF was removed under reduced pressure. The crude reaction mixture was then extracted into CHCl₃ (200mL) and passed through a short pad of silica (CHCl₃ eluent). The CHCl₃ organic layer was then washed with water (3x 200mL), dried (Na₂SO₄) and then filtered. The organic layer was then removed under reduced pressure, and the crude material was twice subjected to silica gel column chromatography (eluent systems listed below), until all di-octyl-NDI and NH₂-Ph-Bpin (0.95 eq helps here) were removed. The column can be stripped using neat EtOAc. The product is an off-white solid (1g, 10% yield).

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 8.80 (m, 4H), 8.02 (d, J = 8.04 Hz, 2H), 7.33 (d, J = 8.04 Hz, 2H), 4.21 (t, J = 5 Hz, 2H), 1.76 (m, 2H), 1.37 (s, 12H), 1.35 (m, 10H), 0.88 (t, J = 5Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 163.15, 163.05, 137.45, 136.29, 131.62, 131.28, 128.05, 127.34, 127.25, 127.11, 126.95, 84.18, 41.34, 32.08, 29.56, 29.47, 28.37, 27.37, 25.15, 22.91, 14.37.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{37}\text{BN}_2\text{O}_6$ (M+H) $^+$: 581.28234, found 581.28257.

Chromatography eluent systems:

CH_2Cl_2 : THF. 500: 1 > Through 300: 1, then strip with Hexane: EtOAc. 5: 1.

Synthesis of the BDX-Ph-Bpin building block.

The synthesis of **BDX-2**, **BDX** and **BDX-B(OH) $_2$** has previously been reported.²⁻³

Figure S3. Synthesis of the **BDX-Ph-Bpin** building block.

Reagents and Conditions: (i) 5% Pd-C, H_2 , THF, 40psi, r.t., 24hrs (92%) (ii) 2-methoxypropene, PPTS, Benzene, reflux, 24hrs (80%) (iii) $^n\text{BuLi}$, THF, 0°C , 1hr, $\text{B}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3$ at -78°C (iv) 1-Bromo-4-iodobenzene, THF/ H_2O 10:1, K_2CO_3 , $\text{Pd}(\text{dppf})\text{Cl}_2$, reflux (62%) (v) B_2Pin_2 , 1,4-dioxane, $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{K}$, $\text{Pd}(\text{dppf})\text{Cl}_2$, reflux (66%).

BDX-B(OH)₂ is very sensitive to column chromatography. If the stoichiometry of the borylation reaction is controlled accurately, this compound can/ should be used immediately in the next step without further purification.

Synthesis of the BDX-Ph-Br.

BDX-Ph-Br

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with **BDX-B(OH)₂** (5 g, 0.019 mol, 1eq), 1-Bromo-4-iodobenzene (6.38g, 0.023 mol, 1.2eq), and THF/ H₂O 10:1 (200 mL: 20mL). The resulting mixture was then subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. K₂CO₃ (7.8g, 0.056 mol, 3eq), and Pd(dppf)Cl₂ (275mg, 2 mol%) were then added, and the reaction was set to reflux for 48 hrs. Upon cooling to r.t. the reaction mixture was passed through a short pad of celite (washing with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 100mL)) to remove any palladium by-products. The organic layer was then washed with water (3 x 100mL), brine (3 x 100mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The organic layer was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: CH₂Cl₂ / 2:1), yielding **BDX-Ph-Br** as a white solid (4.4 g, 62%).

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 7.70 (d, J = 10Hz, 2H), 7.53 (d, J = 10Hz, 2H), 6.32 (s, 2H), 1.68 (s, 12H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 141.05, 138.22, 131.64, 131.39, 130.87, 121.68, 118.17, 107.51, 92.44, 25.99.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrO}_4$ [M^+]: 376.0304, found 376.0317.

Synthesis of the **BDX-Ph-Bpin**.

BDX-Ph-Bpin

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with **BDX-Ph-Br** (4g, 0.011 mol, 1eq), B_2Pin_2 (4.04g, 0.016 mol, 1.5eq), and 1,4-dioxane (200 mL). The resulting mixture was then subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{K}$ (3.12g, 0.032 mol, 3eq), and $\text{Pd}(\text{dppf})\text{Cl}_2$ (155mg, 2 mol%) were then added, and the reaction was set to reflux for 24 hrs. Upon cooling to r.t. the reaction mixture was passed through a short pad of celite (washing with CH_2Cl_2 (3 x 100mL)) to remove any palladium by-products. The organic layer was then washed with water (3 x 100mL), brine (3 x 100mL), dried over Na_2SO_4 and filtered. The organic layer was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: CH_2Cl_2 / 20:1), yielding **BDX-Ph-Bpin** as a white solid (3.06 g, 68%).

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.87 (d, $J = 10\text{Hz}$, 2H), 7.78 (d, $J = 10\text{Hz}$, 2H), 6.32 (s, 2H), 1.67 (s, 12H), 1.35 (s, 12H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 140.95, 138.49, 135.23, 134.90, 128.53, 118.03, 108.64, 92.32, 83.99, 25.98, 25.12.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{29}\text{BO}_6$ [M^+]: 424.2056, found 424.2078.

Synthesis of the reference molecules and final molecules.

Synthesis of the $\text{B}(\chi)\text{-(Ph)}_2$.

$\text{B}(\chi)\text{-(Ph)}_2$

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with $\text{B}(\text{R})\text{-5}$ (500mg, 0.98 mmol, 1eq), 4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-2-phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolane (602mg, 2.95 mmol, 3eq), and THF/ H_2O 10:1 (100 mL: 10mL). The resulting mixture was then subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. K_2CO_3 (408mg, 2.95 mmol, 3eq), and $\text{Pd}(\text{dppf})\text{Cl}_2$ (15mg, 2 mol%) were then added, and the reaction was set to reflux for 48 hrs. Upon cooling to r.t. the reaction mixture was passed through a short pad of celite (washing with CH_2Cl_2 (3 x 100mL)) to remove any palladium by-products. The organic layer was then washed with water (3 x 100mL), brine (3 x 100mL), dried over Na_2SO_4 and filtered. The organic layer was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: EtOAc / 6:1), yielding $\text{B}(\text{R})\text{-(Ph)}_2$ as a white solid (404 mg, 80%).

Data for $\text{B}(\text{R})\text{-(Ph)}_2$

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.46 (Ar ABC, 4H), 7.36 (Ar ABC, 2H), 7.23 (Ar ABC, 4H), 3.51 (s, 6H), 2.47- 2.23 (m, 8H), 1.99 (s, 6H), 1.66 (m, 8H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 153.59, 142.58, 141.87, 134.12, 130.72, 130.25, 129.77, 129.65, 128.63, 128.58, 126.67, 126.57, 60.00, 29.13, 28.38, 23.68, 23.22, 14.48.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$ ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$: 525.2764, found 525.2766.

Data for **B(S)-(Ph)₂**

Yield 77%.

^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.46 (Ar ABC, 4H), 7.36 (Ar ABC, 2H), 7.23 (Ar ABC, 4H), 3.51 (s, 6H), 2.47- 2.23 (m, 8H), 1.99 (s, 6H), 1.66 (m, 8H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 153.59, 142.58, 141.87, 134.12, 130.72, 130.25, 129.77, 129.65, 128.63, 128.58, 126.67, 126.57, 60.00, 29.13, 28.38, 23.68, 23.22, 14.48.

ESI-MS calcd. For $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$ ($\text{M}+\text{Na}$) $^+$: 525.2764, found 525.2749.

A general one-pot Suzuki coupling protocol was employed to furnish **1 χ** and **1 α** .

Synthesis of **1 χ** . (General one-pot Suzuki coupling protocol).

A two-neck flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and a reflux condenser was placed under an argon atmosphere. The two-neck flask was then charged with, **B(R)-5** (500mg, 0.98 mmol, 1eq), **NDI-Ph-Bpin** (685 mg, 1.18 mmol, 1.2eq), **BDX-Ph-Bpin** (501 mg, 1.18 mmol, 1.2 eq)., and THF/ H_2O 10:1 (100 mL: 10mL). The resulting mixture was then subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. K_2CO_3 (408mg, 2.95 mmol, 3eq), and $\text{Pd}(\text{dppf})\text{Cl}_2$ (15mg, 2 mol%) were then added, and the reaction was set to reflux for 48 hrs. Upon cooling to r.t. the reaction mixture was passed

through a short pad of celite (washing with CH₂Cl₂ (3 x 100mL)) to remove any palladium by-products. The organic layer was then washed with water (3 x 100mL), brine (3 x 100mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The organic layer was removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: EtOAc / 8:1), yielding (*R*)-**1** as an off-white solid (194 mg, 18%).

Data for (*R*)-1.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 8.67 (m, 4H), 7.81 (d, J = 10Hz, 2H), 7.25 (m, 4H), 7.10 (m, 2H), 6.17 (s, 1H), 4.06 (t, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 3.36 (s, 6H), 2.29- 2.21 (m, 8H), 1.91 (s, 3H), 1.87 (s, 3H), 1.63-1.44 (m, 8H), 1.57 (s, 12H), 1.31-1.09 (m, 12H), 0.72 (t, J = 7.7Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 163.38, 163.06, 153.88, 153.81, 142.74, 142.50, 141.51, 140.82, 134.36, 134.08, 133.13, 131.61, 131.37, 130.96, 130.87, 130.76, 130.72, 130.15, 129.64, 129.49, 129.16, 129.07, 128.75, 128.72, 127.39, 127.27, 127.16, 127.08, 126.73, 126.71, 67.37, 60.08, 41.36, 32.08, 29.57, 29.48, 29.26, 29.22, 28.41, 28.38, 27.39, 26.10, 23.69, 23.65, 23.23, 22.92, 14.69, 14.66, 14.37.

ESI-MS calcd. For C₇₀H₇₀N₂O₁₀ (M⁺): 1098.5025, found 1098.5034.

Data for (*S*)-1.

Yield 22%.

¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 8.67 (m, 4H), 7.81 (d, J = 10Hz, 2H), 7.25 (m, 4H), 7.10 (m, 2H), 6.17 (s, 1H), 4.06 (t, J = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 3.36 (s, 6H), 2.29- 2.21 (m, 8H), 1.91 (s, 3H), 1.87 (s, 3H), 1.63-1.44 (m, 8H), 1.57 (s, 12H), 1.31-1.09 (m, 12H), 0.72 (t, J = 7.7Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (101.0 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 163.38, 163.06, 153.88, 153.81, 142.74, 142.50, 141.51, 140.82, 134.36, 134.08, 133.13, 131.61, 131.37, 130.96, 130.87, 130.76, 130.72, 130.15, 129.64, 129.49, 129.16, 129.07, 128.75, 128.72, 127.39, 127.27, 127.16, 127.08, 126.73, 126.71, 67.37, 60.08,

41.36, 32.08, 29.57, 29.48, 29.26, 29.22, 28.41, 28.38, 27.39, 26.10, 23.69, 23.65, 23.23, 22.92, 14.69, 14.66, 14.37.

ESI-MS calcd. For $C_{70}H_{70}N_2O_{10}$ (M^+): 1098.5025, found 1098.5008.

Synthesis of **2**. (General one-pot Suzuki coupling protocol).

Building blocks:

B(α)-4 (500mg, 1.08 mmol, 1eq), **NDI-Ph-Bpin** (753 mg, 1.29 mmol, 1.2eq), **BDX-Ph-Bpin** (551 mg, 1.29 mmol, 1.2 eq).

Silica gel column chromatography (eluent system Hexane: EtOAc / 4:1), yielding **2** as an off-white solid (221 mg, 22%).

1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm): 8.83 (m, 4H), 7.92 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.73 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.43 (m, 6H), 6.34 (s, 1H), 4.22 (t, 7.7 Hz, 2H), 2.05 (s, 6H), 2.03 (s, 6H), 1.77 (m, 2H), 1.72 (s, 12H), 1.47-1.25 (m, 10H), 0.89 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (101.0 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 163.33, 163.22, 140.81, 137.98, 138.75, 138.69, 138.07, 138.03, 137.75, 136.72, 136.67, 136.64, 136.59, 136.40, 131.69, 131.33, 131.30, 131.10, 130.60, 128.05, 127.44, 127.25, 127.11, 126.95, 126.90, 121.24, 117.89, 107.50, 92.15, 25.71, 41.30, 32.01, 29.55, 29.49, 28.32, 27.37, 22.90, 14.35, 19.60, 19.58.

ESI-MS calcd. For $C_{62}H_{58}N_2O_8$ (M^+): 958.41877, found 958.41996.

2. Electrochemical Data

A CH instruments electrochemistry workstation (CHI660A) was used for electrochemistry experiments. A platinum wire counter electrode, a glassy carbon working electrode, and a silver wire reference electrode were used for both cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) experiments. CH_2Cl_2 was used as the solvent, TBAPF_6 was used as the electrolyte (0.1 M), and ferrocene was used as an internal reference ($E(\text{Fc}/\text{Fc}^+) = 0.45 \text{ V vs. NHE}$).⁴ Scan rate = 0.05 V/s.

Figure S4. Cyclic Voltammograms (CV) (Left) and Differential Pulse Voltammograms (DPV) (Right) of (S)-1 recorded in CH_2Cl_2 at 295 K. TBAPF_6 was used as the electrolyte (0.1 M), Scan rate = 0.05 V/s.

Figure S5. Cyclic Voltammograms (CV) and Differential Pulse Voltammograms (DPV) of **B(χ)-(Ph)₂** recorded in CH₂Cl₂ at 295 K. TBAPF₆ was used as the electrolyte (0.1 M), Scan rate = 0.05 V/s.

Figure S6. Cyclic Voltammograms (CV) (Left) and Differential Pulse Voltammograms (DPV) (Right) of **2** recorded in CH_2Cl_2 at 295 K. TBAPF_6 was used as the electrolyte (0.1 M), Scan rate = 0.05 V/s.

3. Transient Absorption Spectroscopy

Femtosecond transient absorption (fsTA) and nanosecond transient absorption (nsTA) experiments were conducted in PrCN at 105 K using a commercial Ti:sapphire laser system (Tsunami oscillator/Spitfire amplifier, Spectra-Physics) as described previously.⁵ The 355 nm pump pulses were generated using a commercial collinear optical parametric amplifier (TOPAS-Prime, Light-Conversion, LLC) and attenuated to 1 $\mu\text{J}/\text{pulse}$. Pump pulses underwent randomized polarization (DPU-25-A, Thorlabs Inc.) to suppress the contribution from polarization-dependent dynamics. TA spectra were detected using a customized Helios/EOS spectrometer and Helios software (Ultrafast Systems, LLC). The optical density of each sample was 0.4-0.6 at 355 nm in a 2 mm cuvette. The sample was mounted in a VNF-100 cryostat (Janis Research Company, LLC) between two copper plates to afford thermal contact. The temperature was monitored and controlled using a Cryo-Con 32B temperature controller (Cryogenic Control Systems, Inc.). The spectroscopic data sets were corrected for group delay dispersion and scattered light using Surface Explorer (Ultrafast Systems, LLC) prior to kinetic analysis. The kinetic analysis was performed using MATLAB as described previously.⁶

Figure S7. a) Femtosecond transient absorption spectra of *(S)*-1 following 355 nm excitation in PrCN at 105 K. b) Kinetic traces and fits at selected wavelengths. c) Evolution-associated spectra obtained from global fitting. d) Model populations as a function of time.

Figure S8. a) Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of (S)-1 following 355 nm excitation in PrCN at 105 K. b) Kinetic traces and fits at selected wavelengths. c) Evolution-associated spectra obtained from global fitting. d) Model populations as a function of time.

Figure S9. a) Femtosecond transient absorption spectra of *(R)*-1 following 355 nm excitation in PrCN at 105 K. b) Kinetic traces and fits at selected wavelengths. c) Evolution-associated spectra obtained from global fitting. d) Model populations as a function of time.

Figure S10. a) Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of (*R*)-**1** following 355 nm excitation in PrCN at 105 K. b) Kinetic traces and fits at selected wavelengths. c) Evolution-associated spectra obtained from global fitting. d) Model populations as a function of time.

Figure S11. a) Femtosecond transient absorption spectra of **2** following 355 nm excitation in PrCN at 105 K. b) Kinetic traces and fits at selected wavelengths. c) Evolution-associated spectra obtained from global fitting. d) Model populations as a function of time.

Figure S12. a) Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of **2** following 355 nm excitation in PrCN at 105 K. b) Kinetic traces and fits at selected wavelengths. c) Evolution-associated spectra obtained from global fitting. d) Model populations as a function of time.

4. Electron Paramagnetic Resonance Spectroscopy

The X and W band EPR measurements were performed on a Bruker Elexsys E680 X/W EPR spectrometer equipped with a split ring resonator (Bruker ER4118X-MS3) at X band and a cylindrical resonator (Bruker EN-680-1021H) at W-band. The temperature was kept at 85K using an Oxford Instruments CF935 continuous-flow cryostat cooled with liquid nitrogen and an ITC503S temperature controller.

The Q-band measurements were performed on a home-built instrument described previously⁷ but with several changes and modifications, for completeness it will be described again. The microwaves were generated with a Keysight M8190A Arbitrary Waveform Generator at an intermediate frequency of between 0.5 and 2.5 GHz and upconverted to 33.2 and 35.2 GHz in a custom Millitech/Smiths interconnect microwave bridge. The bridge outputs maximally ~6 W in high power pulse mode and ~10 mW in continuous wave mode. On the detection end, the signal is first amplified with a Pasternack 22 dB gain low noise amplifier (PEWGA3208) and then down-converted to baseband with a pair of mixers in quadrature, further amplified using a pair of Femto variable gain voltage amplifiers (DHPVA-201) and finally digitized using an Acqiris SA220P DAQ card. The magnetic field was generated using a GMW model 3474-140 magnet and was controlled with a Lakeshore F-41 Gaussmeter. The laser and the AWG were triggered coherently using a Stanford DG645 delay generator. Temperature was maintained at 85 K using an Oxford Instruments CF935 Cryostat with liquid nitrogen and an ITC503S temperature controller. The experiments were run with resonant frequencies of around 34 GHz using a Bridge12 loop-gap resonator (B12TQLP). The instrument was controlled with Specman4EPR a commercially-available control software.⁸

The sample was photoexcited at 355 nm with a 7-ns, 1-mJ laser pulses generated via an output of a frequency-tripled Nd:YAG laser (Spectra-Physics Quanta-Ray Lab-150+-10H) operating at a repetition rate of 10 Hz. The laser light was coupled into the resonator via a fiber optic (Thorlabs FT1000UMT) and collimator placed outside the cryostat window or, in the case of W band, via top excitation directly from the fiber.

All EPR measurements were performed in the glassy solvent butyronitrile (PrCN) (Sigma-Aldrich). Solutions with an O.D. of 0.5-0.9 over a 2 mm pathlength were loaded into quartz tubes (2.40 mm o.d., 2.00 mm i.d. at X band, 1.5mm o.d., 1.00mm i.d. at Q band), subjected to three freeze-pump-thaw cycles on a vacuum line (10^{-3} Torr), and sealed with a hydrogen torch. The samples were flash frozen with liquid nitrogen and then quickly loaded into the already cold resonator at 85 K. Solutions for W-band experiments were loaded into quartz tubes (0.86 o.d., 0.6 i.d.) and loaded into a cold resonator at 85 K.

Transient continuous-wave EPR (TREPR) spectra were collected at X band and Q band and processed according to previously published procedures⁹. At W-band, two pulse Hahn echo detected field swept spectra were collected 150ns following photoexcitation using a $\pi/2 - \tau - \pi$ pulse sequence with pulses shaped by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG). Pulse lengths of $\pi/2 = 20$ ns and $\pi = 40$ ns were used to collect the full transient trace of the echo at each field both with and subsequently without photoexcitation. The dark spectrum was subtracted from the light spectrum and plotted. All processing and fitting of the spectra were performed in MATLAB using home written scripts and the simulation package EasySpin v6.0-dev.54¹⁰.

Out-of-phase electron spin echo envelope modulation (OOP-ESEEM) spectroscopy was collected at X band 50 ns following photoexcitation using a two-pulse, $\pi/4 - \tau - \pi$, pulse sequence. Microwave pulses were generated using a 1 kW TWT amplifier (Applied Systems Engineering

117X) and shaped using an AWG in a partially over-coupled resonator to minimize ringing. Using pulse lengths of $\pi/4 = 10$ ns and $\pi = 20$ ns, the pulse sequence was started at $\tau = 100$ ns and incremented $\Delta\tau = 10$ ns, a standard 4-step phase cycle was utilized, and the full transient trace of the spin echo intensity was recorded. The time domain OOP-ESEEM traces were fit to equation (S1)¹¹:

$$S(\tau) = e^{-\frac{\tau}{T_d}} \int_0^\pi \sin(J + D(\theta)) \tau W(\theta) \sin \theta d\theta \quad (\text{S1})$$

where T_d is the relaxation time, J is the exchange coupling and $D(\theta)$ is the dipolar coupling and $W(\theta)$ is the weighting function accounting for all orientations of the powder spectrum. The dipolar coupling takes the form:¹⁰

$$D(\theta) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi\hbar} \frac{g_D g_A \beta_e^2}{r_{DA}^3} (1 - 3\cos^2\theta) \quad (\text{S2})$$

which was also introduced as the constant $D = 52.04 \text{ MHz nm}^3/r_{DA}^3$. The weighting spectrum took the form $W(\theta) = \sin \theta$. The OOP-ESEEM fits, and their parameters are shown in Table S1. Figure S13 shows the OOP-ESEEM was performed on (S)-**1**, (R)-**1** and **2**. The extracted and DFT-calculated distances are shown in Table S1. The experimentally determined distances are 2.32 ± 0.01 nm for **2** and 2.36 ± 0.01 nm and 2.38 nm for (S)-**1** and (R)-**1**, respectively. This indicates that the electron-electron coupling was approximately the same for (S)-**1**, (R)-**1** and **2**.

Figure S13. OOP-ESEEM (black) and their fit (red) of A) **2**, B) (*S*)-**1**, and C) (*R*)-**1**.

Table S1. The fitted values from OOP-ESEEM and DFT calculations.

Compound	J (MHz)	Experimental radical pair distance (nm)	DFT calculated distance (nm)
(<i>S</i>)- 1	0.2 ± 0.1	2.36 ± 0.01	2.36
(<i>R</i>)- 1	0.3 ± 0.1	2.38 ± 0.01	2.37
2	0.4 ± 0.1	2.32 ± 0.01	2.37

Table S2. Simulation parameters for (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1** and **2** in glassy PrCN at X-, Q- and W-bands. The simulation of **2** assumes an initial singlet state, while the simulations of (*S*)-**1** and (*R*)-**1** assume an initial spin state as determined by eq 9 (main text) with χ in degrees as a variable that is stated in this table.

	X	Q	W
<i>g</i>	BDX: [2.0058 2.00524 2.00228] NDI: [2.0044 2.0042 2.0021]	BDX: [2.0058 2.00524 2.00228] NDI: [2.0044 2.0042 2.0021]	BDX: [2.0058 2.00524 2.00228] NDI: [2.0044 2.0042 2.0021]
<i>g</i> Frame (degrees)	BDX: [30 90 0] NDI: [0 90 0]	BDX: [30 90 0] NDI: [0 90 0]	BDX: [30 90 0] NDI: [0 90 0]
<i>g</i> Strain	BDX: [0 0.0015 0.002] NDI: [0.018 0 0]	BDX: [0.0006 0 0.001] NDI: [0.001 0.0006 0.0004]	BDX: [0.0003 0.0001 0.0005] NDI: [0.0003 0.0002 0.0003]
Linewidth pp (mT)	0.05	0.15	0.08
Distance (nm)	2 : 2.32 (<i>S</i>)- 1 , (<i>R</i>)- 1 : 2.36	2 : 2.32 (<i>S</i>)- 1 , (<i>R</i>)- 1 : 2.36	2 : 2.32 (<i>S</i>)- 1 , (<i>R</i>)- 1 : 2.36
Hyperfine Interaction (MHz)	BDX: ¹ H [0.368 5.295 3.225] NDI: ¹ H [-4.982 -4.341 -6.782] ¹ H [-4.645 -4.01 -6.484] ¹ H [-4.536 -4.037 -6.420] ¹ H [-5.05 -4.255 -6.76] Simulated with hybrid method.	N/A	N/A
χ (degrees)	51 ± 3	37 ± 4	45 ± 3
% CISS	38 ± 0.04	21 ± 0.05	29 ± 0.08

5. Density Functional Theory Calculations

Geometry optimization calculations of (*S*)-**1**, (*R*)-**1** and **2** were performed using density functional theory (DFT) at B3LYP/6-31G* level of theory in Qchem (version 6.1.0).¹² The DFT optimized structures are shown in Figure S14. Hyperfine coupling constants of the optimized radical ions were calculated using DFT at B3LYP/EPR-II level of theory using ORCA (version 5.0.4).¹³

Figure S14. DFT-optimized structures using B3LYP/6-31G* level of theory. (a) (*R*)-**1**, (b) (*S*)-**1** and (c) **2**.

Geometries for the compounds

(*R*)-**1**

C	12.75809	-0.87104	0.31314
C	13.43731	0.32513	0.51704
C	12.60072	1.43089	0.62178
C	11.21612	1.35129	0.52682
C	10.51126	0.15089	0.32725
C	11.37312	-0.95583	0.22840
O	11.00866	-2.27214	0.03620

C	12.23624	-3.02199	-0.15806
O	13.31824	-2.11877	0.18094
O	12.98792	2.73470	0.81810
C	11.77225	3.50247	1.00277
O	10.67732	2.61410	0.65855
C	12.25226	-4.19600	0.80558
C	12.35200	-3.40893	-1.62732
C	11.77631	4.67411	0.03604
C	11.64944	3.89448	2.47003
C	9.03592	0.06296	0.23573
C	8.34872	-1.08787	0.66186
C	6.96046	-1.16409	0.57969
C	6.20211	-0.10103	0.06764
C	6.88791	1.04431	-0.35859
C	8.27582	1.12863	-0.27714
C	4.70640	-0.17269	-0.01590
C	4.08867	-0.69580	-1.17220
C	2.68305	-0.72991	-1.26048
C	1.90337	-0.23008	-0.19441
C	2.54226	0.26764	0.95045
C	3.94067	0.29901	1.06501
C	0.40242	-0.23069	-0.23554
C	-0.31968	0.72987	-0.97785
C	-1.72815	0.71359	-0.95789
C	-2.40474	-0.25053	-0.17945
C	-1.69881	-1.20394	0.57537
C	-0.29615	-1.18018	0.52347
C	-3.90425	-0.24052	-0.12275
C	-4.56876	0.48630	0.87748
C	-5.95977	0.51487	0.94051
C	-6.70608	-0.18324	-0.00687
C	-6.06907	-0.91570	-1.00536
C	-4.67564	-0.94479	-1.05727
O	1.76996	0.67396	2.02583
O	0.41632	-2.06792	1.31076
N	-8.15262	-0.13216	0.04537
C	-8.77209	1.03147	-0.45976
C	-10.25650	1.08298	-0.37236
C	-10.97516	0.00272	0.19378
C	-10.30795	-1.14786	0.67951
C	-8.82387	-1.23950	0.60749
C	-10.93240	2.19735	-0.84327
C	-12.33567	2.26851	-0.76129
C	-13.06096	1.22500	-0.20828
C	-12.39237	0.07533	0.27717
C	-13.11179	-1.00294	0.84594

C	-12.43777	-2.11945	1.31392
C	-11.03436	-2.19195	1.23012
C	-14.54398	1.31887	-0.12727
N	-15.21016	0.22455	0.45012
C	-14.59360	-0.93556	0.94106
C	-16.67411	0.27140	0.55421
O	-15.26527	-1.83616	1.42164
O	-15.15539	2.29362	-0.53808
O	-8.20826	-2.21029	1.01154
O	-8.11398	1.93992	-0.93575
C	4.96431	-1.18594	-2.31959
C	4.23183	-2.06808	-3.33454
C	2.89349	-1.43679	-3.71348
C	1.99517	-1.34101	-2.47699
C	0.43665	1.81315	-1.73896
C	-0.39908	2.53000	-2.80308
C	-1.74583	2.94763	-2.21448
C	-2.53770	1.71262	-1.77705
C	4.58771	0.81806	2.32932
C	-2.40442	-2.22351	1.44125
C	0.71541	-3.32067	0.70554
C	1.47274	2.06483	2.07959
H	14.51585	0.38976	0.58771
H	12.17296	-3.83180	1.83339
H	13.18500	-4.75854	0.69986
H	11.41100	-4.86488	0.59948
H	12.32917	-2.50910	-2.24917
H	11.51826	-4.05661	-1.91508
H	13.29370	-3.93693	-1.80628
H	11.86175	4.30667	-0.99013
H	12.62294	5.33459	0.24729
H	10.84902	5.24723	0.13320
H	11.65479	2.99581	3.09393
H	10.71372	4.43546	2.64080
H	12.48974	4.53166	2.76244
H	8.90654	-1.92741	1.06049
H	6.45168	-2.06210	0.92213
H	6.32413	1.88143	-0.76302
H	8.77669	2.02909	-0.61357
H	-3.98476	1.03557	1.61084
H	-6.46663	1.08267	1.71492
H	-6.66045	-1.45899	-1.73601
H	-4.17986	-1.51735	-1.83635
H	-10.35693	3.01071	-1.27224
H	-12.87176	3.13798	-1.12638
H	-13.01333	-2.93172	1.74502

H	-10.49823	-3.06170	1.59473
H	-17.00433	1.22962	0.16020
H	-16.97187	0.16058	1.59935
H	-17.11202	-0.55049	-0.01748
H	5.83205	-1.71977	-1.91875
H	5.38100	-0.31154	-2.84332
H	4.05033	-3.06280	-2.90189
H	4.86509	-2.21931	-4.21739
H	2.38634	-2.01772	-4.49390
H	3.06742	-0.43310	-4.12814
H	1.65026	-2.35377	-2.21656
H	1.08290	-0.78516	-2.71538
H	1.34312	1.39588	-2.18708
H	0.79707	2.56237	-1.01692
H	-0.56580	1.86474	-3.66287
H	0.15495	3.39868	-3.17970
H	-2.33407	3.52497	-2.93814
H	-1.57403	3.60461	-1.34934
H	-2.92218	1.20242	-2.67414
H	-3.42750	2.01881	-1.21780
H	3.86806	0.82470	3.15021
H	4.96946	1.83934	2.19858
H	5.44343	0.20126	2.61945
H	-3.27100	-1.78857	1.94641
H	-1.71942	-2.61576	2.19529
H	-2.77816	-3.06972	0.84902
H	1.19412	-3.92901	1.47736
H	1.40836	-3.20254	-0.13656
H	-0.19255	-3.83090	0.35553
H	0.82955	2.36984	1.24495
H	2.38425	2.67762	2.07112
H	0.93864	2.22923	3.01908

(S)-1

C	15.23809	-0.77010	0.20460
C	15.91556	0.42993	0.38950
C	15.07551	1.53205	0.50349
C	13.68959	1.44552	0.43355
C	12.98565	0.24095	0.25233
C	13.85203	-0.86232	0.14411
O	13.49248	-2.18280	-0.03003
C	14.72027	-2.92395	-0.25361
O	15.80211	-2.01616	0.07199
O	15.46043	2.83941	0.68056
C	14.24564	3.59893	0.89841
O	13.14908	2.70810	0.56615

C	14.76220	-4.10508	0.70035
C	14.81061	-3.30024	-1.72777
C	14.22451	4.78132	-0.05478
C	14.14958	3.97520	2.37226
C	11.50942	0.14571	0.18464
C	10.83658	-1.02154	0.59024
C	9.44786	-1.10571	0.53022
C	8.67214	-0.03461	0.06254
C	9.34288	1.12665	-0.34428
C	10.73160	1.21905	-0.28517
C	7.17544	-0.11867	0.01404
C	6.52881	-0.57713	-1.15415
C	5.12230	-0.63061	-1.20496
C	4.36676	-0.23304	-0.07990
C	5.03667	0.18991	1.07927
C	6.43686	0.25691	1.15022
C	2.86368	-0.25806	-0.08606
C	2.13627	-1.22547	0.64234
C	0.72841	-1.19636	0.62773
C	0.05399	-0.19535	-0.10446
C	0.76247	0.75654	-0.85782
C	2.16524	0.70250	-0.83468
C	-1.44492	-0.13658	-0.08370
C	-2.21320	-0.80059	-1.05195
C	-3.60528	-0.73838	-1.03064
C	-4.24747	-0.01210	-0.02963
C	-3.50514	0.65435	0.94257
C	-2.11320	0.59287	0.90974
O	4.30356	0.44234	2.23290
O	2.86997	1.56010	-1.66987
N	-5.69397	0.04826	0.00465
C	-6.37957	-1.10454	0.44729
C	-7.86447	-1.01745	0.49122
C	-8.52057	0.17644	0.10613
C	-7.78851	1.30551	-0.33429
C	-6.30260	1.25706	-0.39867
C	-8.60337	-2.10976	0.91754
C	-10.00839	-2.04387	0.97326
C	-10.67289	-0.88533	0.60294
C	-9.93928	0.24292	0.16296
C	-10.59556	1.43713	-0.22057
C	-9.85843	2.52982	-0.64820
C	-8.45349	2.46337	-0.70608
C	-12.15850	-0.83286	0.66971
N	-12.76126	0.37227	0.27084
C	-12.07839	1.51879	-0.16055

C	-14.22581	0.47120	0.31900
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O	-12.82494	-1.78405	1.04916
O	-5.63472	2.20476	-0.77412
O	-5.77542	-2.11079	0.77497
C	7.37387	-0.99662	-2.35151
C	6.62682	-1.87554	-3.35830
C	5.27385	-1.24981	-3.69055
C	4.39975	-1.16568	-2.43514
C	2.89181	-2.31877	1.38752
C	2.03981	-3.09782	2.39450
C	0.69951	-3.48500	1.77331
C	-0.08661	-2.22393	1.40516
C	7.11328	0.70599	2.42654
C	0.05615	1.80839	-1.68428
C	3.28050	2.80500	-1.11614
C	3.88011	1.78413	2.44277
H	16.99487	0.49953	0.43989
H	14.69187	-3.74950	1.73170
H	15.70033	-4.65453	0.57704
H	13.92688	-4.78240	0.49851
H	14.77043	-2.39679	-2.34324
H	13.97581	-3.95174	-2.00353
H	15.75190	-3.82164	-1.92710
H	14.29599	4.42560	-1.08600
H	15.06927	5.44544	0.15143
H	13.29442	5.34522	0.06466
H	14.16927	3.07051	2.98689
H	13.21583	4.51209	2.56541
H	14.99326	4.61237	2.65480
H	11.40514	-1.86792	0.95695
H	8.95306	-2.01771	0.85550
H	8.76736	1.97140	-0.71491
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H	-4.19216	-1.25655	-1.78267
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H	-8.07608	-3.01228	1.20757
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H	-14.61701	-0.51352	0.56363
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H	-14.52602	1.19819	1.07834
H	8.27699	-1.50797	-2.00298

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H	6.47142	-2.87844	-2.93490
H	7.23789	-2.00399	-4.26034
H	4.74936	-1.82359	-4.46462
H	5.43213	-0.24115	-4.09832
H	4.01310	-2.16978	-2.20070
H	3.52521	-0.54600	-2.64315
H	3.75204	-1.88393	1.90008
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H	2.59152	-3.98316	2.73377
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H	0.87521	-4.09090	0.87269
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H	-0.98220	-2.49359	0.83597
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H	-0.82763	1.40037	-2.18244
H	0.72924	2.21048	-2.44382
H	-0.29376	2.64433	-1.06371
H	3.66955	3.39847	-1.94784
H	4.07409	2.66903	-0.37229
H	2.43820	3.34003	-0.65691
H	3.10028	2.07379	1.72861
H	4.71928	2.48914	2.37018
H	3.46801	1.82281	3.45475

2

C	12.92514	-1.14747	0.15502
C	13.68554	0.00750	0.01184
C	12.92346	1.16103	-0.13384
C	11.53331	1.16190	-0.14124
C	10.74479	0.00471	0.00665
C	11.53502	-1.15098	0.15739
O	11.08540	-2.44466	0.32355
C	12.25459	-3.30457	0.32556
O	13.40519	-2.42419	0.31888
O	13.40149	2.43843	-0.29862
C	12.24941	3.31682	-0.30168
O	11.08199	2.45457	-0.31112
C	12.26334	-4.11718	1.61041
C	12.25676	-4.13806	-0.94930
C	12.26094	4.13993	-1.57957
C	12.24587	4.13997	0.98010
C	9.26469	0.00310	0.00366

C	8.53303	-1.00858	0.65352
C	7.14252	-1.00728	0.64839
C	6.41122	-0.00109	-0.00376
C	7.14291	1.00751	-0.65168
C	8.53345	1.01284	-0.64966
C	4.92799	-0.00368	-0.00802
C	4.20529	-1.20323	-0.06872
C	2.80810	-1.22577	-0.07287
C	2.09640	-0.00879	-0.01449
C	2.80345	1.21076	0.04664
C	4.20069	1.19329	0.04874
C	0.59574	-0.01139	-0.01614
C	-0.11247	0.04947	-1.23508
C	-1.50986	0.04465	-1.21675
C	-2.23373	-0.01487	-0.01861
C	-1.51178	-0.07343	1.18076
C	-0.11445	-0.07479	1.20152
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C	-5.83401	0.75179	-0.95457
C	-6.53014	-0.00966	-0.01788
C	-5.83548	-0.77447	0.91733
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C	2.07313	2.53452	0.12208
C	2.08296	-2.55220	-0.15077
C	0.61707	0.11326	-2.55935
C	0.61284	-0.13634	2.52723
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C	-10.12111	-1.15599	-0.42658
C	-8.63334	-1.17995	-0.44477
C	-10.80739	2.28400	0.83295
C	-12.21482	2.28802	0.84083
C	-12.92331	1.16782	0.43548
C	-12.23235	0.00780	0.00955
C	-12.93385	-1.14879	-0.40781
C	-12.23743	-2.27292	-0.82219
C	-10.82982	-2.27610	-0.83216
C	-14.41082	1.19015	0.45078
N	-15.05924	0.01670	0.02865
C	-14.42006	-1.15590	-0.39974
C	-16.52755	-0.00950	0.02844
O	-15.07707	-2.12621	-0.74598
O	-15.04094	2.17318	0.81033

O	-8.00252	-2.15715	-0.80801
O	-7.98169	2.15015	0.77456
H	14.76825	0.00850	0.01341
H	12.25743	-3.44271	2.47094
H	13.16072	-4.74165	1.65546
H	11.38031	-4.76175	1.65683
H	12.24817	-3.47824	-1.82162
H	11.37059	-4.77930	-0.98286
H	13.15274	-4.76533	-0.98864
H	12.26077	3.47241	-2.44550
H	13.15638	4.76773	-1.61578
H	11.37599	4.78196	-1.62443
H	12.23950	3.47321	1.84715
H	11.35649	4.77652	1.01755
H	13.13871	4.77125	1.02518
H	9.05824	-1.79847	1.17627
H	6.61282	-1.78851	1.18696
H	6.61378	1.78737	-1.19276
H	9.05902	1.80404	-1.17009
H	4.74412	-2.14448	-0.14190
H	4.73580	2.13652	0.12375
H	-2.04591	0.06098	-2.16214
H	-2.04936	-0.08955	2.12528
H	-3.90868	1.37253	-1.66185
H	-6.37988	1.35609	-1.67210
H	-6.38282	-1.37575	1.63631
H	-3.91127	-1.40094	1.62304
H	1.39455	2.67430	-0.72766
H	2.78069	3.36926	0.12978
H	1.45741	2.61020	1.02675
H	2.79389	-3.38401	-0.16352
H	1.46430	-2.62739	-1.05341
H	1.40799	-2.69780	0.70098
H	1.23192	1.01796	-2.64057
H	-0.09009	0.11346	-3.39452
H	1.29694	-0.73635	-2.69200
H	-0.09606	-0.13801	3.36093
H	1.29028	0.71500	2.66100
H	1.22955	-1.03961	2.61006
H	-10.24658	3.15682	1.14997
H	-12.76656	3.16442	1.16372
H	-12.79832	-3.14635	-1.13772
H	-10.27751	-3.15171	-1.15633
H	-16.87568	0.96275	0.36876
H	-16.88297	-0.79989	0.69382
H	-16.89197	-0.21865	-0.97993

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